

Teacher Creativity Skills in Overcoming Limitations of Learning Infrastructure at Alkhairaat Labuha Middle School

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A B S T R A C T

This research aims to examine and analyze Teacher Creativity Skills in Overcoming Limited Learning Facilities at Alkhairaat Labuha Middle School. The method for writing this article is library research techniques. Reference sources in this writing are taken from published books and scientific articles. The benefit of this writing is to find out Teacher Creativity Skills in Overcoming Limited Learning Facilities at Alkhairaat Labuha Middle School. The results of the research revealed: 1) The facilities and infrastructure for skills lessons are inadequate, 2) the condition of the infrastructure for skills lessons is less supportive because the equipment is old, 3) Teachers have a creative attitude shown by the ability to see problems, look for ideas and ideas in skills lessons.

INTRODUCTION

Teachers are the main axis of education. It determines the progress of a country in the future. A teacher is a person who educates, provides teaching, provides guidance, adds physical or non-physical training, provides assessments, and carries out periodic evaluations related to one or more sciences for all students. In general, the teacher's job is to teach students to have knowledge and skills in each subject area. Apart from that, teachers also have the responsibility to educate students to have good attitudes and behavior, whether in the school environment or the community.

The teacher's task is to guide students in their development to become adults. Adults in this context are people who have faith, established knowledge and noble character. In carrying out your duties as a teacher, of course, there are obstacles or problems you will face. The educational problem that occurs in Indonesia is the lack of educational infrastructure, especially in remote areas. This creates a gap in the quality of education. Many students cannot enjoy the same facilities and infrastructure as students in the city.

However, amidst these limitations, of course, as teachers we do not lose our enthusiasm and neglect our duties as educators. A teacher must have a professional, competent nature and be able to follow developments in science and technology. Therefore, a professional teacher is required to be creative amidst limitations such as a lack of facilities or infrastructure in a school. Teachers must be able to think about how to ensure that students can continue to learn through technological developments even amid limitations. So, every child in Indonesia can continue to receive proper education.

Skills are the ability to use reason, thoughts, ideas and creativity in doing, changing or making something more meaningful to produce value from the results of the work. The aim of learning skills for junior high school students is to provide students with skills for competition in the era of globalization. Many factors influence the smoothness and success of educational learning at school, especially skills. These factors include the curriculum, environment, students, teachers, facilities and infrastructure.

Lack of tools and facilities as a dominant factor in the success of skills learning must be overcome. Schools as providers of formal education must have adequate facilities and infrastructure so that the educational process can run well. Likewise with skills lessons, as education whose implementation is practical, it must be supported by adequate facilities and infrastructure for smooth learning. In conditions like this, teachers are required to be able to overcome existing problems so that teaching and learning activities continue and students can understand and understand the material being presented.

Facing these problems, the most important thing is how skills teachers can be creative so they can convey lesson material well so that skills learning objectives can be achieved. To make it easier to search for data from research on several problems determined by the object under study, several problems are formulated as follows: How is the creativity of skills teachers in overcoming limited facilities and infrastructure in skills learning at Alkhairaat Labuha Middle School?

Creativity according to Musbikin (2006: 6) is the ability to start ideas, and see new or unexpected relationships. Apart from that, the ability to formulate concepts that are not just memorizing, create new answers to existing questions and get new questions that need to be answered. These characteristics differ in motivation, intellect and personality. Creative nature can be demonstrated by the ability to see problems around them, being able to create ideas or thoughts to solve problems and being open to new things.

According to Syaiful Bahri Djamarah (2010: 43-48), the teacher's role is as corrector, inspirer, informant, organizer, motivator, initiator, facilitator, guide, demonstrator, class manager, mediator, supervisor and evaluator. To a certain extent, teachers can also teach creative skills (how to think about dealing with problems creatively or techniques for generating original ideas). Skills like these can be taught directly, but are best taught by example. The characteristics of a creative teacher are having the ability to see problems during teaching and learning activities, create ideas during teaching and learning activities and apply new things in learning. Skills subjects are oriented towards creating work results that are supported by a person's knowledge, attitude and creativity. Students are expected to have the ability to understand skills, be skilled, and be creative. The material provided at Alkhairaat Labuha Middle School includes crafts, processing technology and cultivation technology. Infrastructure influences the smooth learning of skills.

According to Barnawi & Arifin (2012: 40), educational facilities include all equipment and supplies that directly support the educational process, educational infrastructure includes all equipment and supplies that indirectly support the educational process. Infrastructure is very important to use in teaching and learning activities. The existence of supporting facilities means students are more comfortable and can easily understand the material taught at school.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In writing this Journal Article, the researcher explored information from several previous studies as comparison material, both regarding existing advantages and disadvantages. Apart from that, researchers also dig up information from books, theses, theses and journals in order to obtain previously existing information about theories related to the title used to obtain a scientific theoretical basis.

1. Research conducted by Jelita Dalimunthe and Sapri Sapri, entitled: Teacher Creativity in Overcoming the Lack of Facilities and Infrastructure for Learning Jurisprudence. This research aims to determine the creativity of a teacher in overcoming the lack of fiqh learning facilities and infrastructure at MAS Raudhatul Akmal Batang Kuis, as well as the condition of fiqh learning facilities and infrastructure at MAS Raudhatul Akmal Batang Kuis. To support education, facilities and infrastructure are very important. Supporting the success of studying jurisprudence, various supporting elements are very important. One of them is with the help of jurisprudence textbooks, with the existence of jurisprudence textbooks

teachers are helped in developing teaching materials and enable students to participate fully in their learning. If jurisprudence learning textbooks are insufficient, teachers are expected to be able to creatively overcome these problems so that the learning process can be successful and students can achieve their jurisprudence learning goals. The results of this research show: 1) MAS teacher Raudhatul Akmal Batang Kuis is a teacher who is creative in overcoming the lack of facilities and infrastructure for learning jurisprudence. 2) MAS teacher Raudhatul Akmal Batang Kuis is a teacher who is creative in looking at problems. 3) The condition of the MAS Raudhatul Akmal Batang Kuis fiqh learning facilities and infrastructure is inadequate.

2. Research conducted by Pingky Meilina Cahayani, et al, entitled: level of teacher creativity to overcome limited infrastructure and facilities in the PJOK learning process in junior high schools in Sukoharjo District, Sukoharjo Regency in 2020. that there are still many PJOK infrastructures and facilities that are not as adequate as they should be. However, it is not yet proportional to the number of students, there are still many teachers who are not creative enough in making tool modifications, and many teachers are still waiting for assistance with PJOK infrastructure and facilities from the school. This research aims to determine the level of creativity of teachers to overcome limited infrastructure in the PJOK learning process in junior high schools in Sukoharjo District, Sukoharjo Regency. This research is quantitative and descriptive. The method used in this research is a survey method with data collection techniques using questionnaires as primary data, as well as observation and documentation as secondary data. The population of this study were all PJOK teachers in junior high schools in Sukoharjo District, Sukoharjo Regency, totaling 23 teachers. The data analysis used is descriptive percentage analysis. The results of the research found that the creativity of physical education teachers, sports and health in responding to limited physical education facilities and infrastructure in junior high schools in Sukoharjo District, Sukoharjo Regency as a whole was categorized as 1 teacher (4%) in the very high category, 6 teachers (26.09%) in the very high category. high category, 10 teachers (43.48%) in the medium category, 4 teachers (17.39%) in the low category, and 2 teachers (8.70%) in the very low category. It can be concluded that the creativity of sports and health physical education teachers in responding to limited physical education facilities and infrastructure in junior high schools in Sukoharjo District, Sukoharjo Regency is in the medium category (43.48%).

METHODS

This research uses qualitative research to obtain information about teacher creativity and skills in overcoming limited infrastructure. Implementation of research at Alkhairaat Labuha Middle School. The method the author uses in writing this article is library research techniques. Writing a study or literature

review is a movement to collect information from various sources of understanding (Harahap: 2014).

Research methods are scientific ways to obtain data with specific purposes and uses. To achieve this goal requires a method that is relevant to the goals to be achieved. Writing this journal uses a literature review approach with qualitative methods. Literature review research is research that processes and collects research materials in the form of library data which can be obtained from books or journals (Hatch, 2002). The choice of this method was based on considering the availability of data in various media which examines theories related to independent learning as an effort to improve the quality of learning in schools/madrasahs. The data collection method is documentation, namely tracing various data in the form of online documents, articles, books and notes which will be analyzed using an educational analysis approach (Merriam, 1988).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Creativity of Skills Teachers at Alkhairaat Labuha Middle School

Everyone should know the importance of being creative in every aspect of life, know how to learn it, and how creativity can be used as a tool to help solve various problems. Creativity means creating, discovering, imagining, conceptualizing, forming, constructing, producing, producing, looking into the future or the ability to predict new trends, the ability to analyze market or society needs, the ability to preserve nature, and so on. So, creativity is very complex and has many sides (Chen, 2010).

Creativity is an important ability for a person to have. Creativity as an idea must be transformed into reality, that is, transformed into innovation. According to Munandar (1988), creativity can be understood as a personal characteristic of an individual and not a social characteristic that is shared by society) which is reflected in his ability to create something new. The same thing was also expressed by Selo Somardjan in Munandar, 1988). He said that creativity begins with an individual's ability to do better (Prihatin, Benedicta. 2019).

One teacher and another teacher are the same. They both have teaching diplomas, have IV certificates, passed the test as teachers, and they even both have certificates as professional educators. So, what differentiates one teacher from another? One of the things that differentiates it is its creativity. A teacher's ability to create new learning models or create new impressions will differentiate him from other teachers. Teachers who have high creativity can be said to be creative teachers. Creative teachers will not languish in just delivering the material. He always thinks about how to ensure that the material taught can be understood by students and they feel happy when studying the material.

There are several reasons why teachers need to be creative, including:

1. With a creative spirit, students will be interested in what the teacher teaches
2. The lessons taught by the teacher will be interesting
3. Students will be enthusiastic about learning
4. Students will become more independent
5. Students will find it easier to solve problems

6. Teachers can provide diverse inspiration to students about various problems and solutions
7. The creativity of teachers in teaching will make students become individuals who can realize themselves fully through the ideas they produce
8. The teaching and learning process becomes more enjoyable
9. Students will become more independent and students will find it easier to solve problems and students will be happier facing challenges
10. Can bring satisfaction to teachers and students

Creative teachers will always look for ways to carry out their activities to achieve the desired targets. His mind will be filled with creative thoughts. What does creative thinking look like? The following will explain how creative thoughts a teacher has.

- a. Sensitive to Problems

Teachers who have creative thinking tend to be sensitive to various problems around them. He always monitors developments happening around him. When problems arise around them, the teacher will quickly try to find a solution. So, before the problem becomes more widespread, teachers can handle it. Being sensitive to problems needs to be developed because students often find it difficult to express the problems they experience. Teachers should be sensitive to changes that occur in students so that the problems they face can be resolved as soon as possible.

- b. Lots of Ideas

Teachers who have creative thinking have lots of smart ideas. If a problem occurs, he will be able to solve the problem with his brilliant ideas. At a meeting, for example, when other teachers have not been able to propose a solution to the problems that are occurring, creative teachers will quickly offer their ideas.

- c. Flexible Fast and Attractive

A teacher who has creative thinking tends to be flexible in carrying out various activities and easily adapts to the environment. People who think creatively tend to be able to adapt to current developments. A creative teacher also tends to be unconventional. If currently everyone has switched from manual typewriters to computers, creative teachers can easily adapt to this new tool. When the latest curriculum is launched, creative teachers can easily learn and understand it.

- d. Have Strong Motivation

To become a reliable motivator, someone must become a motivator for themselves first, including teachers. Great teachers tend to be able to motivate themselves and their students well. So, apart from providing material, teachers also provide strong motivation and examples of good attitudes and behavior for their students. A person's strong motivation can be seen in his actions. Teachers do too. Teachers who have strong motivation will work seriously. The motivation that exists in teachers will influence their students. They will imitate teachers and motivate themselves to become superior individuals.

- e. Have the ability to concentrate

A teacher who can organize his creative thinking well will have good concentration abilities so he can carry out his profession well. The ability to concentrate plays an important role in solving various problems. Without good concentration, the person will experience failure, he will not be able to focus his attention to solve the problem. As a result, he was unable to solve various problems because he never focused on solving problems one by one. High concentration is also needed to solve problems in urgent situations. When pressed, only people who can concentrate will be able to act appropriately. Calmly, he will take the right action so that the problem can be resolved well. Likewise teachers. A calm and concentrated attitude when facing problems in class will make problem-solving smooth. On the other hand, when teachers are not calm, it is feared that their actions will trigger panic.

Teachers also known as educators are adults who are responsible for providing guidance or assistance to students in their physical and spiritual development so that they reach maturity, able to carry out their duties as creatures of Allah, caliphs on the surface of the earth, as social creatures and as individuals who can stand alone. Another term commonly used for educators is teacher. Teachers can provide the role and color of a nation in the context of implementing education so that it deserves attention (Mustafa, Hermandra, & Zulhafizh, 2018).

Teachers are educators and instructors in early childhood education through school or formal education, basic education and secondary education. Such teachers must have some kind of formal qualification. In a broader definition, anyone who teaches something new can also be considered a teacher. (<https://id.wikipedia.org/wiki/Guru>). Teachers are professional educators in their field who have the main task of educating, teaching, guiding, giving direction, providing training, providing assessments, and conducting evaluations for students who pursue their education from an early age through formal government channels in the form of Elementary School to Middle School (Law No. 14 of 2005).

According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary, skills are "the ability to complete tasks". Skills are abilities possessed by a person that are obtained from various exercises and learning. Teaching skills are a manifestation of a teacher's ability as a professional. While teaching is "training". (KBBI, 2007). Skills teachers have a creative attitude in practical learning, this is done to overcome the limited infrastructure for skills lessons so that learning can continue and can be understood by students. The creative attitude of the skills teacher is carried out in the following way:

1. Ability to See Problems

Teachers can train field skills to a certain extent, and teach creative skills when facing problems to come up with new ideas as problem solvers. Knowledge and experience are expected to be problem solvers so that learning continues. Teacher's Ability to Create Ideas. Teacher's ability to create ideas, it can be concluded that teachers are included in the creative category in creating ideas in skills learning. Creating ideas or notions to achieve learning success, especially in learning skills in junior high school is not an easy way. This can be done if the

teacher has not studied much or has experience in teaching lessons. The results of this research illustrate that the skills teachers at Alkhairaat Labuha Middle School are creative in delivering lessons by providing learning strategy ideas. As stated by Melvin L. Silberman (2013: 35), the physical environment in the classroom can support or hinder active learning activities. The infrastructure and layout of the classroom during teaching and learning activities are fun and challenging. This can make students active and not bored during teaching and learning activities.

2. Be open to new things

Teachers are open to new things in overcoming the limited infrastructure and facilities for learning skills at school. The research results show that skills teachers always try to develop themselves, especially in aspects of learning at school. Information is obtained from various sources such as the internet, books, experience and conducting experiments before providing learning to students. Skills lessons are experiencing development, this is in line with advances in science and technology which require skills lessons to become learning that can be applied outside of school.

The results of research on teacher creativity and skills in overcoming limited infrastructure in schools. It was concluded that the creativity of skills teachers in overcoming limited infrastructure and skills lessons is included in the creative category. Skills teachers can overcome limited infrastructure in learning skills which include crafts, processing technology and cultivation technology. The results of this research show that limited infrastructure is not an obstacle to optimizing skills learning. A good teacher is a teacher who can be creative in optimizing existing learning resources, especially overcoming limited facilities and infrastructure. As stated by Munandar (2012: 19), creativity is a lifestyle, a way of perceiving the world. Living creatively means developing your talents, and learning to use your abilities optimally. Exploring new ideas, new places, new activities, developing sensitivity to environmental problems, other people's problems, and humanitarian problems.

Facilities and Infrastructure for Skills Lessons at Alkhairaat Labuha Middle School

One of the factors that supports the success of educational programs in the learning process is facilities and infrastructure. Educational infrastructure and facilities are some of the resources that serve as a benchmark for school quality and need continuous improvement in line with the development of quite sophisticated science and technology. Educational facilities and educational infrastructure are not the same. Educational facilities are all facilities (equipment, accessories, materials and furniture) that are directly used in the teaching and learning process, both movable and non-movable to achieve educational goals and run smoothly, regularly, effectively and efficiently, such as buildings, classrooms, desks and chairs, as well as teaching media equipment, libraries, school offices, student council rooms, parking lots, laboratory rooms. Educational infrastructure is a facility that indirectly supports the educational or teaching process, such as a yard, garden or school garden, the road to school, school rules and regulations, and so on. The emphasis in this definition is on its

nature, facilities are direct and infrastructure is indirect in the educational process. (Barnawi & M. Arifin. 2012.)

Etymologically (linguistically) infrastructure means indirect tools to achieve goals in education, for example: location/place, school buildings, sports fields, money and so on. Meanwhile, means direct tools to achieve educational goals. For example: Room, Books, Library, Laboratory and so on. Educational facilities are all kinds of equipment used by teachers to facilitate the delivery of lesson material. When viewed from the student's point of view, educational facilities are all kinds of equipment that students use to make it easier to learn subjects (Arikunto, 1993). Educational infrastructure is all kinds of equipment, equipment and objects used by teachers and students to facilitate the implementation of education (Daryanto, 2006).

According to Mulyasa (2003) educational facilities are equipment and supplies that are directly used and support the educational process, especially the teaching and learning process, such as buildings, classrooms, tables, chairs, as well as teaching tools and media. Bamawi (2012), believes that educational infrastructure is all the basic equipment that indirectly supports the implementation of the educational process in schools. Facilities and infrastructure are all movable and immovable objects or goods that are used to support the implementation of direct and indirect learning processes in education (Rohit, 2006). Therefore, educational facilities and infrastructure are a unit that supports the implementation of the learning and teaching process well and optimally. (Suhelayanti et al. 2020).

To implement effective and efficient school learning activities, management of school facilities and infrastructure is required. Management of educational facilities and infrastructure can be interpreted as the process of procuring and utilizing components that directly or indirectly carry out the educational process to achieve educational goals effectively and efficiently. Infrastructure management can be interpreted as a cooperative process of utilizing all educational facilities and infrastructure effectively and efficiently. This definition shows that existing facilities and infrastructure must be utilized and managed for the benefit of the learning process. The management of facilities and infrastructure is intended so that their use can run effectively and efficiently. Management of educational facilities and infrastructure is tasked with organizing and maintaining educational facilities and infrastructure so that they can contribute to the educational process optimally and meaningfully. These management activities include planning, procurement, supervision, inventory storage, and write-off activities. Use utilization and responsibility. (Indrawan, Idrus. 2015).

One of the educational problems that is often encountered in Indonesia is the problem of inadequate school facilities and infrastructure. Facilities and infrastructure are supporting factors for the success of educational programs. Facilities and infrastructure need to be implemented to support students' skills so they are ready to compete against rapid technology. Facilities and infrastructure are important parts that need to be prepared carefully and continuously so that a smooth teaching and learning process can be guaranteed.

However, in reality, educational facilities and infrastructure in schools in Indonesia, especially in remote areas, are still not implemented optimally. Many areas in Indonesia do not yet have adequate facilities and infrastructure, namely schools in rural areas. This is very different from urban areas where facilities and infrastructure are better than rural areas. The many differences in facilities and infrastructure between urban and rural areas mean that education in rural areas is still very minimal compared to education in urban areas.

In this case, facilities and infrastructure greatly influence the teaching and learning process. Meanwhile, currently, the facilities and infrastructure for education are inadequate many facilities and infrastructures are not suitable for the teaching and learning process. Such as inadequate facilities and infrastructure, namely leaking classroom buildings, damaged or insufficient school benches, waterlogged fields, incomplete books in libraries, inadequate use of technology and information and so on. When school facilities and infrastructure are inadequate it will affect the teaching and learning process carried out. that is, it will hinder the teaching process.

Teachers will find it difficult to provide and explain the material that will be presented to students. Likewise, students will find it difficult to understand what the teacher explains. Therefore, the teaching and learning process will not run effectively and efficiently. A teacher must have professional characteristics, be competent and be able to follow developments in science and technology. For example, in the use of computer technology. In this case, teachers must be able to operate computers, carry out computer-based teaching processes, and so on. If the above facilities are adequate and managed well, the facilities and infrastructure will run as optimally as possible and the talents and interests of students can be further developed, thus creating good student graduates.

Schools do not have space for practice and the number of equipment for practicing skills is limited and does not match the number of students. Skills lessons should have practice space and equipment that supports the learning process. As stated by Barnawi & Arifin (2012: 40), educational facilities include all equipment and supplies that directly support the educational process, educational infrastructure includes all equipment and supplies that indirectly support the educational process.

Based on information obtained from interviews, observations and documentation, the research findings regarding the condition of the infrastructure for skills lessons at Alkhairaat Labuha Middle School are as follows: the condition of the infrastructure is basic and simple, the existing equipment to support the smooth practice of skills is not very good. The reason is the unavailability of space to store equipment and the maintenance of skilled equipment is not optimal.

This is proven by observations that skills equipment is not stored properly because there is no special room for practical equipment. The research results do not match the opinion expressed according to Barnawi & Arifin (2012: 40), Facilities and infrastructure management includes the steps of planning, procurement, regulation, use and elimination. From this knowledge, it is hoped that more attention will be paid to equipment and facility maintenance.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of research and discussion, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Teachers have a creative attitude shown by the ability to see problems, look for ideas and ideas in learning skills so that the limited infrastructure at school does not hinder learning and the lessons can be accepted by students.
2. Skills learning infrastructure is inadequate, practice space and land are not available and supporting equipment is limited.
3. The condition of infrastructure and facilities for skills lessons is not very supportive because the equipment is old and not well maintained.
4. The teacher proposes to the principal to provide space and space to practice skills so that students can practice comfortably and the practical learning process can run smoothly.
5. Teachers must ensure that the placement of equipment for practice carried out outside the classroom is neat so that students are not crowded together when carrying out practice.
6. The teacher proposes to the school to find a technician to maintain the practical equipment that is already available at the school.
7. Students must pay more attention to the directions and advice given by the teacher. School and class rules must be obeyed by every student and implemented well.
8. Students must be active and play a role in the smooth learning of skills.

FURTHER STUDY

Writing this journal article uses a literature review approach with qualitative methods. Literature review research is research that processes and collects research materials in the form of library data which can be obtained from books or journals (Hatch, 2002). This literature study can be used as a guide for further research, namely descriptive and analytical research so that we can get a picture of Teacher Creativity and skills in Overcoming Limited Learning Facilities at Alkhairaat Labuha Middle School.

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